

USING NEW LEVEL METHODS IN SPEAKING AROUND STRANGE POSITION

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Abstract: Everyone makes mistakes, even speakers using their own language when they are hurried, 'lost for words', or forced into inappropriate language by a difficult or unusual situation. It is hardly surprising, then, that language learners make mistakes, given the difficulty of the task of comprehending, processing the content of the message and knowledge of the target language, and coming out with a response that is both grammatically correct and appropriate to the situation.

Key words: Foreign language, methods, innovative ideas, mistakes, learning process.

It is generally agreed that correction is part of the teaching/learning process, but that over-correction and poor correction techniques can be demotivating for the learner and may lead to a reluctance to try out new language or even to speak at all. Teachers need to make informed decisions about what, when and how to correct in order to help learners improve their speaking skills without damaging their confidence. Errors are produced as a result of the lack or misinterpretation of knowledge, which, in turn, may be a product of the learner's stage of language development or of inadequate teaching or learning. Errors cannot be corrected and need to be dealt with by teaching or reteaching. Errors are often noticed in less-guided practice activities when the same error is made by a number of learners, leading the teacher to realize that something has gone wrong in earlier stages of the teaching/learning process. Mistakes, on the other hand, are products of the learner's efforts to produce language despite prior knowledge. These may be due to a variety of factors including over-enthusiasm, over-generalization of rules and interference from the mother tongue. Once the cause has been established, mistakes can be dealt with by a number of correction techniques.

Mistakes are usually corrected immediately when the aim of the stage of the lesson is to promote accuracy, particularly during the drilling of the target language and during guided practice. Attention to mistakes in these stages improves the chances of correct use of language later, while mistakes made during less-guided practice often indicate that the teacher has not dealt effectively with mistakes at the accuracy stage. When the aim is fluency, however, less intrusive, 'gentle' or delayed correction techniques are required in order not to damage either the flow of the activity or the confidence of the learners.

In the process of acquiring the language, a learner may acquire forms of language that are in between their first language and their target language. This is their 'interlanguage' and is a product of incorrect application of rules, incomplete knowledge and comparison between two (or more) languages. Interlanguage may seem completely logical and correct in the mind of the learner and may also be a part of a natural learning process where rules get more refined as more input is received. This leads to the theory that mistakes are a healthy part of language learning and should not be dealt with too severely. However, if learners are not corrected, mistakes in their interlanguage may 'fossilise' and become permanent.

Oddly, 'good' learners often make more mistakes than others. This tends to be because they have more confidence, produce more language and are highly motivated to speak. Good learners are also 'hypothesis testers', in that they can formulate and try out rules of their own, and 'risk takers', in that they are prepared to 'have a go'. These learners need to be encouraged and are often capable of self-correction. Teachers need to consider the above, get to know their learners and their learning backgrounds, develop an attitude to correction and be equipped with a variety of correction techniques which are appropriate to a variety of learner types and learning situations. Bearing this in mind, here are some activities that teachers might like to try in their classrooms.

Planning time has been shown to increase production in speaking tasks. Lower level learners often find it especially difficult to speak spontaneously, so these activities incorporate 'thinking time' during which learners can prepare for speaking by planning what they are going to say, and asking the teacher or using a dictionary to look up missing vocabulary. The following activities are relatively short, with minimal materials preparation time for the teacher. They are designed for use as a warmer or a filler in the middle or at the end of a class.

Information gap and jigsaw tasks have been shown to be beneficial task types in terms of promoting obligatory, as opposed to optional, information exchange and as a way of promoting collaborative dialogue in the classroom. In this activity, students work in pairs and the information, i.e. the pictures, are divided equally between them. Students must work collaboratively to put the story together in the right order. Suitable for strong pre-intermediate students and above.

Any innovation is nothing more than the creation and subsequent implementation of a completely new component, as a result of which qualitative changes occur in the environment. Technology, in turn, is a collection of different techniques used in a particular business, craft or art. Thus, innovative technologies in preschool educational institutions are aimed at creating modern components and techniques, the main purpose

of which is to modernize the educational process. For this, pedagogical teams of kindergartens are developing the newest models of education and intellectual development of children, which differ from other preschool educational institutions. Educators use methodological tools and methods in their professional activities and fully correspond to the adopted model. Modern preschool educational institutions are used more and more, and the result of their implementation can be seen for more than ten years.

The introduction of innovative technologies in preschool educational institutions includes, among other things, the use of activities called research activities by teachers. What does this mean? The point is, first of all, the efforts of educators are aimed at forming a research type of thinking in children. To do this, in the process of teaching preschool children, teachers resort to common methods: posing a problem, analyzing it comprehensively, modeling, observing, experimenting, determining the results, finding solutions and choosing the best one. It helps innovative "coaches" in preschool educational institutions to find an approach to each child, take into account his characteristics, character traits and turn lessons into an exciting and unusual "adventure". Thanks to this, parents no longer have to persuade their beloved children to go to kindergarten. Children visit with pleasure and enrich their small knowledge base every day.

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